

Optimizing QoS MAC Scheduling in 5G NR: A Lyapunov Approach Evaluated with XR Traffic

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Abstract—5th Generation (5G) and beyond technologies are designed to convey multiple Quality of Service (QoS) requirements coming from highly heterogeneous services. In this regard, 5G extends the QoS definition of previous technologies. In order to fulfill the requirements of new services, it is necessary to develop resource management solutions that effectively and efficiently translate them to usage of resources. Therefore, MAC schedulers are to be designed to accommodate the demands of emerging applications with stringent QoS requirements, such as eXtended Reality (XR). In this work, we introduce a Lyapunov-based Medium Access Control (MAC) scheduler designed to appropriately tackle coexisting heterogeneous QoS flows. The proposed approach allows the implementation of policies that explicitly consider the QoS requirements, as well as an efficient use of allocated resources. The results obtained through extensive experiments over the ns-3 5G-LENA simulator demonstrate that our scheduler guarantees the required time-average bit rate for every QoS flow at every time window, while ensuring the stability of traffic queues for all users.

Index Terms—5G, MAC scheduler, QoS, Lyapunov, XR, ns-3

I. INTRODUCTION

THE emergence of new services and their reliance on mobile networks impose rigorous demands concerning QoS. In order to address this challenge, 5G networks have been designed to accommodate a diverse range of services with varying characteristics. In addition to the increasing capacity requirements of enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) applications, the proliferation of massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) and Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) increase the need to support a much larger number of connected devices and exceptionally reliable communication performance.

Among the new services that are looming, XR is distinguished by a unique set of features. New XR devices, such as glasses or head-mounted displays, impose rigorous demands on User Equipment (UE) concerning power consumption, and performance. Consequently, XR devices cannot solely handle all computational tasks, but require support from other nodes. Through split-rendering, the workload of multimedia generation and augmentation can be efficiently distributed between a powerful XR server and the XR device. Typically, tasks demanding intensive processing, like rendering, are handled by the XR server, while less burdensome mechanisms, such as pose correction, are executed at the XR device. In addition, owing to users interaction with XR applications, XR services exhibit specific traffic patterns, characterized by one or more video streams in the downlink (DL), tightly synchronized

with frequent motion/control updates from the user in the uplink (UL). Lastly, XR is distinguished by its combination of high data rates and stringent latency demands, positioning it between 5G eMBB and URLLC in terms of network requirements.

Nowadays, there exist a multitude of XR applications and services, each characterized by its distinctive user configurations, traffic patterns, and QoS requirements. The performance evaluation of XR wireless solutions for such a diverse range of setups represents a significant challenge. Consequently, [1] proposes to categorize XR use cases into three overarching meta-categories: Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Cloud Gaming (CG).

In each scenario, 5G networks and beyond must be capable of dynamically and efficiently adapting the underlying communication resources to support heterogeneous and demanding traffic flows, including those related to XR services. In this sense, 5G NR introduces an enhanced QoS provisioning framework that defines requirements at flow level.

A critical aspect of ensuring appropriate QoS is MAC scheduling, which determines how radio resources are allocated to traffic flows. Although 5G provides the architectural framework to support XR traffic, the standard does not define the MAC scheduler algorithms, leaving their design and implementation open. Therefore, the development of suitable schedulers tailored to the new QoS management framework introduced by 5G NR is of paramount importance. While in the past many MAC schedulers have been proposed, most of them focus on the overall system performance or statical behavior, without explicitly tackling the QoS at the flow level.

In his seminal work [2], Neely introduced a general framework using Lyapunov techniques for queue stabilization. This framework encompasses both max-weight (or min-drift) methods and the broader min drift-plus-penalty control problem. This approach does not only focus on queue stabilization, but it also facilitates the incorporation of time-average objectives into the decision-making process. In particular, the Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty optimization is a widely used technique that can be effectively applied to queuing networks and other stochastic systems. It stabilizes real or virtual queues, while achieving an optimization objective by minimizing the time-averaged network penalty function. Exploiting this methodology within the context of MAC scheduling, we propose to jointly optimize resource allocation, stabilize traffic queues, and maximize the achieved throughput, while satisfying the QoS requirements of heterogeneous flows from active services.

This is particularly critical for those having dynamic and stringent needs, as those associated with XR.

All in all, the main contributions of this paper are:

- The proposal of a drift-plus-penalty MAC scheduler that enhances the optimization of resource allocation between demanding flows, in particular for XR applications, with high and variable throughput and delay requirements, as outlined in the 5G QoS profiles.
- The proposed scheduler can achieve multiples goals, whose relevance can be configured. We show that it is able to guarantee a minimum data rate, defined in the flow QoS profile, while ensuring an efficient use of allocated resources and the stabilization of the Radio Link Control (RLC) queues.
- We introduce a algorithmic approach that provides an efficient solution to the underlying optimization problem.
- We integrate the proposed solution within the ns-3 5G LENA framework [3], whose scheduling approach is extended by considering a generic solution that can be used to implement Lyapunov-based policies.
- A comparative analysis, based on extensive experiments, is conducted to assess the performance of the proposed solution, comparing it with that of alternative schedulers.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Initially, Section II discusses the background on MAC scheduling in 5G networks, reviews the 5G NR QoS management framework, and introduces XR traffic characterization. Then, Section III identifies some related works, pointing out how we go beyond the state-of-the-art. Section IV introduces our proposed scheduler for 5G-supported QoS based on a drift-plus-penalty control problem. In Section V we describe its integration within the ns-3 5G-LENA network simulator, and then in Section VI we assess its performance, comparing it with other scheduling policies, over different scenarios that consider mixed XR traffics. Finally, in Section VII we summarize the work and outline our future research in this field.

II. BACKGROUND

A. MAC scheduling in 5G NR

The MAC layer of 5G networks facilitates the transmission of data between the physical and radio link control layers, manages the mapping between logical and transport channels, schedules physical resources, performs error correction using Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) and handles random access procedures. Although the MAC scheduling function is defined within the corresponding standards, its logic and algorithms are implementation-dependent. In this way, vendors and radio equipment developers have the flexibility to implement their own algorithms within the MAC scheduler.

Without loss of generality, we focus on DL transmission, where the scheduler is responsible for allocating physical layer resources, with the NR Node B (gNB) determining which UE receives resources in both time and frequency domains. While the access scheme establishes the distribution of radio resources, the scheduler decides the order in which these resources are allocated. As it was the case in Long-Term Evolution (LTE), scheduling decisions can be taken every 1

Transmission Time Interval (TTI), which in LTE was 1 ms and in 5G can be configured with higher flexibility. Thus, the 5G NR scheduler operates similarly to LTE, but with some differences timing-wise, which varies based on the numerology type, and on the current bandwidth, which is significantly larger in 5G. Two frequency ranges are used: below 7 GHz (FR1) and above 24 GHz (FR2).

In the frequency domain, 5G uses Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM), where 12 subcarriers are combined to form a Resource Block (RB), which represents the minimum possible allocation of frequency for a UE. While the Subcarrier Spacing (SCS) is fixed at 15 kHz in LTE, 5G defines multiple values, called numerologies, enabling a variable SCS to cover wide ranges of operating frequencies. Numerology, denoted typically as μ , can range from 0 to 6, and exerts a clear influence on the latency. A larger μ increases the SCS, and allows for greater bandwidth and shorter TTI, making it appropriate for delay-critical services and the mmWave band. On the other hand, in the time domain, a slot consists of 14 or 12 symbols, depending on whether it uses normal or extended cyclic prefix, respectively. The minimum time domain length in a RB can be 1 OFDM symbol, but it varies depending on the Start and Length Indicator Value (SLIV).

The volume of physical time-frequency resources is not the only information available at the MAC scheduler. The following information can be collected in order to facilitate more optimal scheduling decisions:

- **QoS data acquisition.** During the connection with the gNB, each UE establishes one or more QoS flows, identified by their own QoS Flow Identifier (QFI). Therefore, unlike LTE, 5G supports a more granular flow-based QoS framework to ensure an optimal user experience for various types of traffic. Furthermore, MAC scheduling timings for data, retransmission, and feedback can be configured or adjusted based on these QoS requirements. The MAC scheduler obtains QoS data from the Policy Control Function (PCF) [4].
- **Channel State Information (CSI) messages from UE.** The scheduler interacts with UEs to gather real-time data regarding radio channel conditions in terms of CSIs. These CSI reports are sent by UEs on both periodic and aperiodic basis, and are calculated relatively to the SINR and BLER. Typically, the CSI includes Precoding Matrix Indicator (PMI), Rank Indicator (RI), and Channel Quality Indicator (CQI). The gNB can then use this information to choose a number of streams per UE, a precoding matrix, and a Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), all this together with the final Transport Block Size (TBS) [5].
- **Buffer Status.** The RLC layer provides the MAC with the status of the data buffers, i.e. the amount of data currently queued and awaiting transmission for each UE in the DL, or to the gNB in the UL. This information is communicated from the RLC entities by means of Buffer Status Report (BSR) messages, one for each bearer [6].

The scheduler decides the RBs allocation, after which

the Downlink Control Information (DCI) is transmitted over the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) to inform the UEs about the incoming data and the DL scheduling assignments.

B. QoS management within 5G NR

One of the most significant developments in 5G QoS management is the more feasible separation of corresponding responsibilities between the Core Network (CN) and the Radio Access Network (RAN). In LTE, there is a one-to-one mapping between Evolved Packet System (EPS) bearer, S1 bearer, and radio bearer. In contrast, the 5G User Plane Function (UPF) facilitates the mapping of Service Data Flows (SDFs) onto QoS flows [4]. Therefore, the QoS flow is the finest granularity of QoS differentiation in the PDU session. The User Plane traffic with the same QFI within a PDU session is assigned a QoS flow profile, which defines how it should be treated. The QoS flow can be categorized as either Guaranteed Bitrate (GBR) or Non-GBR, based on its QoS profile, which is sent to the RAN and is defined by a number of parameters, including:

- **5G QoS Identifier (5QI).** A scalar value that identifies a set of QoS parameters. The details regarding these parameters are given below.
- **Allocation and Retention Priority (ARP).** This contains information used to handle a flow in certain cases, with limited resources.

For each Non-GBR QoS flow only:

- **Reflective QoS Attribute (RQA).** This optional parameter specifies whether the UE uses the same QoS configuration in UL and DL.

For each GBR QoS flow only:

- **Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (GFBR).** It represents the minimum bit rate that the network guarantees for a specific QoS flow over a certain averaging time window. This parameter ensures that the QoS flow consistently receives the required bit rate, thereby meeting the specific needs of the application or service.
- **Maximum Flow Bit rate (MFBR).** This parameter establishes an upper limit on the bit rate expected from the QoS flow. It sets a maximum threshold for the bit rate, thereby enabling the network to regulate and manage traffic that exceeds this limit. Any excess traffic may undergo shaping or policing mechanisms at various network elements, including the UE, UPF or RAN.
- **Notification control.** It enables the RAN to inform the Session Management Function (SMF) when the GFBR cannot be fulfilled and when it becomes feasible again.
- **Maximum Packet Loss Rate.** It defines an acceptable packet loss rate for the GBR flow.

5QI defines the QoS requirements that should be provided to a given flow. It is used at different RAN layers to facilitate the management of QoS flows. In greater detail, 5QI defines the following parameters:

- **Resource Type.** A GBR QoS flow employs either the GBR resource type or the Delay-critical GBR resource type. The definitions of Packet Delay Budget (PDB) and

Fig. 1: 5G RAN and CN QoS management decoupling through UPF mapping of SDF onto QoS flows.

Packet Error Rate (PER) presented below differ for GBR and Delay-critical GBR resource types, and the Maximum Data Burst Volume (MDBV) parameter is only applicable to the Delay-critical GBR resource type.

- **Priority Level.** Every standardized 5QI is associated with a default value for the Priority Level. In the event of congestion, when it is not possible to meet all QoS requirements for each QoS flow, this parameter can be used to decide which QoS flows are prioritized: the lowest level corresponds to the highest priority. On the other hand, when there is no congestion, the scheduler may prioritize QoS flows based on additional factors, such as resource type and radio conditions.
- **PDB.** It sets an upper limit on the delay a packet can experience between the UE and the N6 termination point at the UPF.
- **PER.** It defines an upper bound for non-congestion packet loss rate.
- **Averaging window.** Each GBR QoS flow shall be associated with an averaging window that represents the duration over which the GFBR and MFBR shall be calculated. By default, it is set to 2 seconds, according to the standardized 5QI values [4, Table 5.7.4-1].
- **MDBV.** Each GBR QoS flow with Delay-critical resource type shall be associated with a MDBV. It denotes the largest amount of data that the RAN is required to serve within a PDB.

There are two possible mappings of SDFs onto QoS flows: one-to-one and many-to-one mappings, as shown in Figure 1. While one-to-one mapping provides finer granularity within the 5G NR RAN, in XR sessions a many-to-one mapping is typically employed. This approach consolidates all SDFs from an XR application into a single QoS flow, thus applying uniform QoS characteristics. These QoS flows are managed by the SDAP layer, which also includes one-to-one and many-to-one mappings.

Besides architectural considerations and mapping options at the UPF and SDAP layers, 5G NR supports QoS management through the reconfiguration of various NR layers, based on individual QoS flow descriptions. For instance, parameters such as PDCP and RLC discard/reordering timers can be adjusted according to the PDB of each flow.

TABLE I: Summary of metrics and parameters considered by each scheduler.

Scheduler	Channel quality	Explicit throughput (GFBR)	Delay	RLC queue stability	RB usage	Programmable parameters
RR						
Best CQI, MR	✓					
Channel-delay aware [7], [8]	✓		✓			
PF, G-PF, D-PF [9], [10]	✓					✓
EXP-PF [11]	✓		✓			✓
QoS-aware [12]	✓		✓			✓
MLWDF, EXP-MLWDF [13]	✓		✓			
Queue-HOL-MLWDF [14]	✓		✓			
eMBB-URLLC [15]	✓		✓			
CDRR [16]	✓		✓			
Lyapunov-based [17]	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Proposed	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

C. Key XR features and 3GPP traffic models

3GPP established the evaluation methodology for XR services in Release 17 [1]. This methodology encompasses various aspects, including the modeling of XR applications, simulation scenarios, traffic models, KPIs, and simulation parameters. The aim was to uncover the limitations of current NR systems in supporting XR applications. Towards this objective, various traffic models have been proposed for VR, AR, and CG applications. Further advancements in XR QoS management within 5G RAN are anticipated with the introduction of additional enhancements in Releases 19 and 20, aimed at achieving XR awareness.

For AR, the traffic model comprises a single-stream (video) model for AR DL and a multi-stream model for AR UL. The multi-stream model entails different possibilities, including one (video), two (pose/control plus scene/video/audio/data), or three streams. Specifically, for the three-stream AR UL scenario, there exist two submodels: Model 3A, which uses aggregated streams for pose/control, scene/video, and audio/data, and Model 3B, which considers pose/control, video I-stream, and video P-stream.

Conversely, VR and CG traffic models include single-stream (video) and multi-stream models (two streams, video + audio/data) for VR/CG DL. For VR/CG UL, a single stream (pose/control traffic) is used. In addition, VR and CG models differ in the statistical characterization of the traffics.

III. RELATED WORK

We now discuss some recent works focusing on MAC scheduling for 5G networks, in particular those considering XR services/applications, pointing out how we differ from them.

The authors in [18] provide a comprehensive survey about the most frequently used MAC schedulers in the literature. As the authors argue, the main drawback of the widely-used Round Robin (RR) algorithm is its strict fairness, as it allocates resources equally, without considering channel conditions. To overcome this, several channel-aware schedulers have been proposed. Examples include the Max Rate (MR), which prioritizes the users with the best MCS, and the best CQI scheduler, which allocates resources based on channel quality. Nevertheless, these approaches tend to hinder users

at the cell edge or those suffering poor coverage, leading to an unfair distribution of radio resources. To address this, the Proportional Fair (PF) algorithm was developed, balancing fair resource sharing with channel state awareness. However, these approaches increase spectral resource consumption and overlook specific service requirements.

Many recent works have focused on resource allocation schemes with the objective of maximizing throughput or minimizing Age of Information (AoI) [7], [8], while simultaneously pursuing other objectives. Several alternative schedulers employ the PF metric as a foundation for their performance indicators. These include for instance the EXP-PF [11] and the GPF [9]. The MLWDF [13] establishes a correlation between packet loss probability and delay of transmitted data, as well as the achieved data rate ratio, which is employed by the PF. Variations of MLWDF, such as EXP-MLWDF, integrate an exponential term with the MLWDF model to prioritize users with poor channel conditions. The Queue-HOL-MLWDF [14] integrates PDB and the RLC queue length into the MLWDF metric, to mitigate packet expiration and prevent buffer overflows.

Research on 5G NR QoS management for XR traffic is very active at the time of writing, making related studies relatively limited. In [10], a demand-based PF is proposed to classify VR and UHD traffics for 5G eMBB scenarios. The QoS-aware scheduler presented in [12] classifies XR and mixed traffic based on the assigned 5QI. The authors of [16] propose a channel and delay weighted response ratio scheduler designed for managing coexisting heterogeneous real-time and eMBB traffic. Their approach includes the development of a prioritization function based on the proximity to the delay bound, packet size, and channel conditions.

The application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) has been shown to enhance network maintenance services and Radio Resource Management (RRM) operations, including traffic steering, Quality of Experience (QoE) estimation and prediction, network slicing, etc. Nevertheless, the majority of existing and current research employs AI/ML in upper layer resource management, where the system can accommodate more latency for decision-making processes [19], [20]. The adoption of AI/ML algorithms for lower-level resource management and scheduling at the slot level

is challenging due to timing limitations, and the scarcity or obsolescence of feedback regarding channel status from the air interface. Furthermore, the application of machine learning principles significantly increases the algorithm complexity. For instance, [21] introduced a random forest algorithm to predict users modulation and MCS, thereby eliminating the dependency on the CSI feedback scheme. In [22], an autoregressive moving average machine learning algorithm was used to predict buffer occupancy and CQI values in the MAC scheduler from historical information. The authors proposed exploiting the one-time resource allocation concept for a specified period, applying Prediction Based Scheduling (PBS) to save PDCCH resources and resource allocation time. However, this approach assumes that the channel state remains stable, without significant changes, during these periods. Classic Reinforcement Learning (RL) methods, such as Q-learning and Policy Gradient, are limited, since they are mostly suitable for problems having small discrete action spaces. As the number of active users increases, the discrete action space grows significantly, making the solution of the underlying optimization problem more challenging [23].

The use of Lyapunov optimization applied to MAC scheduling across various network contexts remains relatively limited. In cloud robotics, a two-tier hierarchical MAC protocol has been proposed to maximize time-averaged quality satisfaction and enhance energy efficiency using Lyapunov techniques [24]. Similarly, [25] presents a MAC layer and power allocation/adaptation mechanism that leverages the Lyapunov stochastic optimization framework. This approach formulates two distinct optimization problems—one stochastic and one deterministic: the first is addressed through convex optimization, while the second is solved via max-weight algorithms or non-cooperative game theory. The framework is adaptable to a variety of MAC schemes with adjustable parameters, allowing the network utility function to achieve optimal values across different MAC configurations, thereby facilitating efficient distributed beam scheduling. In [26] the allocation of radio resources to distinct 5G network slices has been examined through the application of Lyapunov optimization. [27] introduces a zero-latency MAC protocol for cyber-physical systems, exploiting interference to enhance remote state estimation performance. The authors establish closed-form requirements for system stabilization based on Lyapunov theoretical framework and demonstrate superior scalability. In [17], the drift-plus-penalty method is employed to address RB allocation and packet drop decisions in 5G networks. The scheduler seeks to minimize long-term average packet drops subject to satisfying GFBR requirements, ensuring RLC queues stability, and bounding delays.

Table I provides an overview of the most relevant schedulers and the metrics they consider. As it can be seen, our proposal considers most of the metrics frequently used by related works in the scheduling problem, including channel quality for each user, throughput, and delay. Furthermore, Lyapunov-based schedulers define long-term objectives, and so ensure system stability. Both [17] and the proposed solution aim to guarantee a time-average throughput over a sufficiently long period. This is consistent with the definition of the GFBR

as a minimum average rate for each GBR flow within every averaging window. However, the two approaches handle this requirement differently. While scheduler in [17] relies on admission control mechanisms to limit the aggregate throughput of flows below the system's maximum capacity, the proposed solution dynamically prioritizes flows that are further from meeting their GFBR. Moreover, the two schedulers differ in their penalties. While [17] focuses on minimizing long-term average packet drops, the proposed scheduler promotes the efficient utilization of radio resources. This is particularly relevant given that it is the only scheduler that enables improvements in spectral efficiency. Both approaches feature adjustable parameters that can significantly alter its behavior, enabling adaptation to a wide range of scenarios. This flexibility offers enhanced configuration possibilities compared to other approaches, which commonly only consider the PF metric. Considering the potential conflictive nature of the different objectives, the scheduler modeling in Section IV also includes a discussion to bound the delay due to buffering at the RLC layer. To the best of our knowledge, the proposed scheduler introduces a novel approach to radio resource scheduling by jointly addressing multiple objectives specifically defined in the 5QI at flow level while promoting an efficient use of radio resources, and it thus makes a significant contribution to the existing solutions in the literature. In addition, the proposed MAC scheduler has been integrated into 5G-LENA, which provides a suitable framework for practical validation and system-level testing. The use of 5G-LENA allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the scheduler's behavior under realistic radio conditions, heterogeneous traffic profiles, and standardized 3GPP-compliant network configurations.

IV. SYSTEM MODEL, PROBLEM FORMULATION, AND SOLUTION

This section describes the design of the scheduler and its relationship with the 5G-specific concepts outlined in Section II. Figure 2 provides an overview of the considered architecture. It illustrates the RLC queues and the virtual queues instantiated by the proposed scheduler at the MAC layer, which are considered in the queue stabilization problem. Finally, this section also discusses the assumptions made and the parameters that can be adjusted to tailor the operation of the proposed solution.

A. Problem formulation

The scheduler considers multiple traffic queues, each characterized by a 5QI and potentially requiring a GFBR. Let \mathcal{N} represent the set of queues, while Λ denotes the available resources (i.e., RBs), and Γ_n corresponds to the GFBR value of each queue. The proposed design aims to maintain stability in the traffic queues, while ensuring compliance with the GFBR, and minimizing resource utilization. For simplicity, we assume that each queue corresponds to a single UE, although a broader approach, mapping queues to Logical Channels (LCs), could also be considered.

Slotted time is assumed, $Q_n(t)$ represents the backlog of queue $n \in \mathcal{N}$ at time slot t , and $\alpha_n(t)$ denotes the scheduling

Fig. 2: System architectural overview.

decision for each queue. Moreover, other stochastic factors exist, like the Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), denoted by $\gamma_n(t)$, and traffic arrivals at the n^{th} queue at slot t is denoted by $a_n(t)$. The evolution of queues in the system, based on incoming and outgoing traffic, $b_n(t)$, is described in Equation (1).

$$Q_n(t+1) = \max\{Q_n(t) - b_n(t), 0\} + a_n(t) \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, we define the instantaneous throughput perceived by the n^{th} user at time slot t as $\rho_n(t)$. Consequently, the incoming and outgoing traffic per queue, as well as the throughput perceived by the corresponding user, can be expressed as generic functions of scheduling decisions and random events, as shown in Equations (2), (3), and (4), respectively. Table II summarizes all the notation used throughout the manuscript.

$$a_n(t) = \hat{a}_n(\alpha_n(t), \gamma_n(t)) = \hat{a}_n(\gamma_n(t)) \quad (2)$$

$$b_n(t) = \hat{b}_n(\alpha_n(t), \gamma_n(t)) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_n(t) = \hat{\rho}_n(\alpha_n(t), \gamma_n(t)) \quad (4)$$

The GFBF is calculated by default using an averaging window of 2 seconds, while scheduling decisions are made in much shorter time units, on the order of milliseconds or lower for high-cardinality numerologies. Our aim is therefore to ensure that the throughput requirement is met on average over time. We consider its time-averaged expectation $\bar{\rho}_n = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}\{\rho(t)\}$. In addition, we aim to minimize the amount of allocated resources, being $f(t) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t)$ the amount of resources allocated at slot t . Since the greedy

TABLE II: Definitions and symbols.

Symbol	Definition
\mathcal{N}	Set of active users. We assume that $\mathcal{N} = \#LCs = \#users$. Additionally, we consider a one-to-one mapping between QoS flows and LCs, which implies a GFBF defined by each LC.
Γ_n	Throughput required by user $n \in \mathcal{N}$.
$Q_n(t)$	RLC queue backlog of the n^{th} LC, or Data Radio Bearer (DRB), at time slot t .
$G_n(t)$	Virtual queue related to throughput achievement of the n^{th} user at slot t .
$a_n(t)$	Arrivals at the $Q_n(t)$, measured in bytes.
$b_n(t)$	Departures from the $Q_n(t)$, measured in bytes.
$\alpha(t)$	Vector of allocated resources at slot t .
$\alpha_n(t)$	Amount of RBs allocated to the n^{th} user at slot t .
Λ	Amount of RBs available to the scheduling decision.
$A(t)$	Admissible decision space at slot t .
$\gamma_n(t)$	Random variable that impacts the performance of resources of user $n \in \mathcal{N}$ at slot t . It accounts for MCS variations.
$\rho_n(t)$	Throughput achieved by the n^{th} user at slot t , as a consequence of the scheduling decision.
$D_n(t)$	Deviation of $\rho_n(t)$ from Γ_n . When $D_n(t) \leq 0$, the throughput target is met for the n^{th} user at slot t .
$K_n^{\text{MCS}}(t)$	Number of bytes per RB that can be dequeued from $Q_n(t)$ based on the current MCS of the n^{th} user at slot t .
$K_n^{\text{TH}}(t)$	Potential throughput per RB for the n^{th} user at slot t .
$\Delta(t)$	Variation in queue length within a given time slot t .
Δ_{\max}^+	Maximum positive value of Δ , which represents the greatest possible increase in the queue.
Δ_{\min}^-	Minimum value of Δ , corresponding to the maximum possible decrease of the queue.
c_{\max}^+	Maximum cost or penalty causing no queue reduction.
c_{\min}^-	Minimum penalty that maximizes queue reduction.
V	Parameter that balances the trade-off between resource usage minimization and backlog reduction.
ω	Weight that adjusts the importance of a specific queue.
$\hat{\cdot}$	It is used to indicate an arbitrary function that yields a variable \cdot .

minimization of resources may hinder the throughput, we include, as an objective, the minimization of average allocated resources, $\bar{f} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{E}\{f(t)\}$. All in all, the scheduler solves the stochastic optimization problem defined in Problem 1, where Equations (6) and (7) ensure that the throughput requirement, Γ_n , is fulfilled, and that the amount of assigned resources does not exceed the available ones, Λ . On the other hand, the scheduler also aims to keep traffic queues $Q_n(t) \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$ mean rate stable, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}\{Q_n(t)\}}{t} = 0$.

Problem 1:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} \bar{f} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{s.t.} \quad \bar{\rho}_n \geq \Gamma_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t) \leq \Lambda \quad \forall t \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Queues } Q_n(t) \text{ are mean rate stable } \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (8)$$

We can now pose the problem in a more concise way, expressing the constraints (7) and (8) in terms of the time-varying admissible decision space, $\alpha(t) \in A(t)$. Besides, we also use a standard formulation by defining $D_n(t) = \Gamma_n - \rho_n(t)$, such that $D_n = \mathbb{E}\{\Gamma_n - \rho_n(t)\} = \Gamma_n - \bar{\rho}_n$. This way, the original problem can be expressed as Problem 2.

Problem 2:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} \bar{f} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \overline{D}_n \leq 0 \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha(t) \in \mathcal{A}(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Queues } Q_n(t) \text{ are mean rate stable } \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (12)$$

B. Optimization with Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty

To address Problem 2, we adopt the framework outlined in [2], which extends the max-weight algorithm. Initially, we define a virtual queue $G_n(t)$ at time slot t , and its value is updated for the next time slot $t + 1$ using Equation (13).

$$G_n(t + 1) = \max\{G_n(t) + D_n(t), 0\} \quad (13)$$

Now the problem can be solved by applying the *min drift-plus-penalty* algorithm [2, Chapter 4], which boils down to solving, at every slot, the following problem:

Problem 3:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} V \cdot \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t) + \omega_1 \cdot \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} Q_n(t)[a_n(t) - b_n(t)] \quad (14)$$

$$+ \omega_2 \cdot \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_n(t)D_n(t)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_n(t) \leq \Lambda \quad \forall t \quad (15)$$

$$b_n(t) \leq Q_n(t) \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (16)$$

where the first term of the objective function, known as the penalty, captures the goal of minimizing allocated resources. Subsequently, the second and third terms, known as the Lyapunov drift, consider the stabilization of traffic queues and virtual queues, designed to fulfill throughput requirements, respectively. Note that the first term is scaled by a design parameter V , which modulates the relative importance the scheduler puts on resource usage minimization versus backlog reduction. When V is set to a large value, the algorithm strongly favors keeping resource usage close to the absolute theoretical minimum, even if it involves punctual increases in queue sizes. In fact, the time-average that we include within the penalty function can get arbitrarily close to an optimal value as $O(1/V)$ at the cost of increasing queue backlogs as $O(V)$. This can be exploited in several scenarios, for instance to promote fair allocation in a distributed environment, while supporting all traffic whenever possible [28]. Furthermore, weights ω_1 and ω_2 are added to the queues to balance out their impact on the scheduling decision. As a result, the configuration of V , ω_1 , and ω_2 allows the scheduler to employ different behaviors. A well-designed configuration enables the algorithm to be better aligned with the desired objectives, more effectively tailored to the requirements and constraints of the specific scenario. A more detailed discussion of possible algorithm configurations is presented in Section IV-D.

Figure 3 provides a functional representation of the proposed algorithm to better illustrate its inputs and outputs. At each time slot, the scheduler performs the following steps:

- 1) Observe the states of $Q_n(t), G_n(t) \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.
- 2) Take the decision that minimizes Problem 3.
- 3) Update queues as defined in Equation (1) and (13).

Fig. 3: Functional diagram of the proposed MAC scheduler, illustrating the flow of inputs and outputs.

C. Sorting-based algorithmic solution

Problem 3 can be simplified by observing that the variables $a_n(t)$ and Γ_n are independent of the decision and, therefore, can be removed from the problem formulation. Additionally, $b_n(t)$ and $\rho_n(t)$ are linear functions of $\alpha_n(t)$ at each time slot, where $\alpha_n(t)$ depends on the MCS. This dependency is illustrated in Equations (17) and (18), with $K_n^{\text{MCS}}(t)$ representing the number of bytes per RB that can be dequeued from $Q_n(t)$ based on the current MCS of the n^{th} user. Similarly, $K_n^{\text{Th}}(t)$ indicates the potential throughput per RB for the n^{th} user.

$$b_n(t) = \alpha_n(t) \cdot K_n^{\text{MCS}}(t) \quad (17)$$

$$\rho_n(t) = \alpha_n(t) \cdot K_n^{\text{Th}}(t) = \alpha_n(t) \frac{K_n^{\text{MCS}}(t)}{t_{\text{slot}}} \quad (18)$$

Hence, the objective function of Problem 3 can be significantly simplified to Equation (19).

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_n(t) [V - \omega_1 \cdot Q_n(t) \cdot K_n^{\text{MCS}}(t) - \omega_2 \cdot G_n(t) \cdot K_n^{\text{Th}}(t)]$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_n(t) \cdot [V - K_n(t)] \quad (19)$$

The optimization problem boils down to Problem 4, which can be tackled with a simple sorting-based procedure, as shown in Algorithm 1. Here, at each slot t , the users are sorted by their value of $K_n(t)$, in ascending order. The algorithm assigns the resources one by one to the first user until its queue $Q_n(t)$ is empty. Furthermore, if the condition $V \leq K \cdot \alpha[u]$ is not met, no additional resources are assigned to minimize resource usage (lines 6-7 in Algorithm 1). Then, the same procedure is applied to the other users. Since Problem 4 is equivalent to Problem 3 and, as with the proposed sorting-based algorithm we are optimally solving Problem 4, the obtained solution is also optimal for Problem 3.

Problem 4:

$$\min_{\alpha(t)} \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_n(t) \cdot [V - K_n(t)] \quad (20)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_n(t) \leq \Lambda \quad \forall t \quad (21)$$

$$b_n(t) \leq Q_n(t) \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (22)$$

Algorithm 1 Sorting algorithm

Input:

- Vector of weights $K \in \mathbb{R}^N$.
- Parameter $V \in \mathbb{N}_0$.
- Vector of users queues $Q \in \mathbb{N}_0^N$.
- Number of resources $\Lambda \in \mathbb{N}$.
- Users ids vector U .

Output:

- Assignment vector $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}_0^N$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \leq \Lambda$.

```

1: procedure ASSIGN( $K, Q, \Lambda, U$ )
2:    $I \leftarrow \text{SortIdx}(K)$ 
3:    $U \leftarrow U[I], K \leftarrow K[I], Q \leftarrow Q[I]$ 
4:    $u \leftarrow \text{PopFront}(U)$ 
5:   for  $r$  in  $\{1, \dots, \Lambda\}$  do
6:     if  $Q[u] > 0$  and  $V \leq K \cdot \alpha[u]$  then
7:        $\alpha[u] ++$ 
8:     else
9:        $u \leftarrow \text{PopFront}(U)$ 
10:    end if
11:  end for
12: end procedure

```

This algorithmic solution is particularly noteworthy as it facilitates the implementation of the scheduler into the 5G-LENA framework, by avoiding the need for an external solver to handle the ILP problem described in Section IV-B. Section V provides further discussion and details regarding such implementation.

D. Scheduler configuration options

The Lyapunov optimization guarantees asymptotic results over the average queue length. In several realistic scenarios, queues are constrained in their capacity, as exemplified by the maximum admissible latency in 5G networks. In these cases, it is necessary to ensure that, during all the time, queue lengths must always be below their maximum capacity. For this purpose, while the Lyapunov drift-plus-penalty theory focuses on the mean values (mean stability), the approach proposed in [29] provides a criterion to enforce a constraint on the maximum value by applying a bound on the parameter V such that the queue never exceeds a target value, Q_{\max} . Moreover, in our case the definition of an upper bound on the maximum queue length allows finding the worst-case delay that a packet might experience while waiting in the queue, thus linking it to the PDB defined in the 5QI. Since delay is not explicitly considered in the scheduler's formulation, this approach provides a way to implicitly bound the delay through the scheduler's configuration, addressing one potential limitation.

In [29], to prevent the queues from exceeding Q_{\max} , the variation in queue length, $\Delta(t)$, is defined as the difference between arrivals, $a(t)$, and departures, $b(t)$, within a given time slot t . Then, the maximum possible variation, Δ_{\max} , is used to define a threshold $Q'_{\max} = Q_{\max} - \Delta_{\max}$, which acts as a safeguard. When the queue backlog reaches this threshold, subsequent actions must reduce the queue length to prevent

overflow. If the system has enough capacity to ensure that this action is feasible, enforcing the constraint only requires satisfying Equation (23).

$$V \leq Q'_{\max} \frac{\Delta_{\max}^+ - \Delta_{\min}^-}{c_{\min}^- - c_{\max}^+} \quad (23)$$

where c_{\max}^+ and c_{\min}^- represent the range of the utility function. In particular, c_{\max}^+ is the maximum cost or penalty (in our case, this is the number of RBs) causing no queue reduction, and c_{\min}^- the minimum penalty that maximizes queue reduction. Δ_{\max}^+ is the maximum positive value of Δ , which represents the greatest possible increase in the queue (equivalent to a_{\max}), and Δ_{\min}^- indicates the minimum value of Δ , corresponding to the maximum possible decrease of the queue (given by $a_{\min} - b_{\max}$).

By setting a V that satisfies Equation (23), it is guaranteed that the queue remains below Q_{\max} , and, consequently, below a maximum delay, which can be defined based on the 5QI PDB. For systems with multiple queues, the analysis extends to ensure that each queue independently adheres to its constraints. V must be chosen as the minimum of all V values derived from individual queues (e.g., different user flows with different 5QI and PDB requirements).

On the other hand, as commented before, queue weights could be used to balance the trade-off between stabilizing traffic queues and guaranteeing the GFBR, especially when both objectives are difficult to achieve simultaneously. The optimal value of these weights depends on the flows characteristics. For high traffic rates, the algorithm may prioritize the stabilization of RLC queues over GFBR compliance. Consequently, increasing the weight of virtual throughput queues in the objective function may prove to be a sensible strategy to yield a performance enhancement or modify the scheduler's behavior according to specific needs or preferences.

V. IMPLEMENTATION IN NS-3

5G-LENA is an open-source 5G NR network simulator, designed as a module that can be integrated in ns-3. The proposed scheduler has been implemented following the design methodology previously used in the NR Module [30]. The core class of MAC schedulers is `NrMacSchedulerNs3`. Scheduling is divided into UL and DL scheduling. In the following, we will focus on DL scheduling, but a similar approach could be applied to the UL case. A radio resource comprises an OFDM symbol in the time domain and a Resource Block Group (RBG) in the frequency domain, where each RBG corresponds to a group of 2, 4, 8, or 16 RBs, depending on the Bandwidth Part (BWP) size. Subsequently, the transmitter allocates power, and the receiver exclusively decodes data among these active RBs. In the 5G-LENA implementation, Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) assigns all RBGs of an OFDM symbol to a single user, whereas Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) can assign different RBGs in each OFDM symbol within a slot to different users. Our implementation is only based on the OFDMA scheme, but it could straightforwardly be applied to the TDMA scheme as well. References to TDMA

may appear, due to inheritance relationships with OFDMA classes. Subclasses using the OFDMA multiple access scheme stem from the `NrMacSchedulerOfdma` class. The available schedulers are:

- **RR.** The available RBGs are allocated among UEs in a cyclical manner, regardless of their CQI or buffer status. This approach provides all UEs with an equal opportunity, which can relatively achieve fairness among UEs. However, it may result in a reduction in throughput, due to CQI independence.
- **MR.** It allocates RBGs to the UE with the best CQI, so it achieves the highest throughput in each TTI. This implies that UEs in areas with suboptimal channel conditions or at the periphery of the cell will be bypassed in the scheduling process, potentially leading to unfairness among UEs.
- **PF.** It assigns RBGs to UEs taking into account their CQI and the previous average throughput. This scheduler is designed to guarantee fairness among UEs, thereby preventing those with poor CQIs from experiencing starvation. UEs are scheduled based on the priority metric K , which can be calculated as shown in Equation (24), where T denotes the data rate potentially achievable for the n^{th} UE in the TTI, and R is the historical average data rate of this UE. In addition, the scheduler behavior can be adjusted by the β value, which varies between 0 and 1. Greater β gives less relevance to the average throughput; therefore, a value of 0, where the actual throughput is neglected.
- **QoS-aware scheduler.** It takes into account the QoS characteristics of a flow based on a combination of QoS indicators and real-time MAC measurements. As a result, it can prioritize delay-critical flows to reduce delay and increase throughput, while meeting their QoS requirements.

$$K = \arg \max_{n=1,2,\dots,N} \frac{T_n^\beta(t)}{R_n(t)} \quad (24)$$

The aforementioned schedulers are integrated into the simulator as classes, wherein they implement virtual functions that update the metrics associated with each UE. These metrics are then accessible on demand to UE-representing classes, which organize the active UEs and allocate resources according to the selected scheduling policy.

In our previous work [31] we discussed the implementation of the linear programming version of the scheduler presented on Section IV. We presented a more detailed description on how the proposed scheduler was integrated into the existing 5G-LENA framework as a new specialization, which required the creation of two new classes (`NrMacSchedulerUeInfoDPP` and `NrMacSchedulerOfdmaDPP`). This initial approach to tackle resource allocation with our scheduler differs from the sorting mechanism employed by the already available solutions. A virtual function is implemented by all scheduler classes, which establishes a loop that invokes a sorting method, together with a comparison function defined within

Fig. 4: UML diagram of the current classes implemented in 5G-LENA (gray) and the new proposed classes (green).

the active scheduler. While the sorting function iteratively allocates demanded or available radio resources within a slot, DPP implementation makes this decision in a single step. This is achieved by solving the underlying Integer Linear Programming (ILP) problem described in Section IV. To accomplish this, we used the GNU Linear Programming Kit (GLPK)¹ optimization tool to solve the corresponding problem instances. Once the UE allocation order is selected, the scheduler assigns the radio resources according to the OFDMA access mode. Subsequently, the DCI messages are generated, based on assigned resources.

To better align with the logic of the function responsible for providing information about assigned resources, and to circumvent the use of external libraries (GLPK), thus easing the integration with 5G-LENA, we propose in this work the implementation of the sorting-based algorithmic solution of the scheduler. Figure 4 presents the corresponding UML diagram.

The scheduler requires, as an input, the total number of available resources (Λ), the occupancy of the RLC queues (Q_n), flows QoS requirements, and channel state. The last one is known through access to the TBS calculation. This also allows the scheduler to estimate the throughput resulting

¹<https://www.gnu.org/software/glpk/>

from the decision, which it is needed to update the virtual throughput queue state at every slot t .

As mentioned earlier, the actual behavior of the proposed scheduler can be configured by means of the parameters V , ω_1 , and ω_2 , from the user example. Consequently, the scheduler operation is rather flexible, enabling it to accommodate various policies.

Finally, while the scheduler is designed to adhere to the GFBR specified per LC, the scheduling process in 5G-LENA is currently implemented in two stages: first at the UE level and then at the LC (i.e., flow) level. Consequently, scheduling decisions are effectively made at the UE level, but with limitations in per-flow differentiation. For this reason, the evaluation in this work has been conducted assuming single-flow UEs, which is still a realistic configuration that allows the proposed scheduler to operate under its optimal conditions. As a practical approximation to support multi-flow UEs, we suggest computing the average GFBR, acknowledging that this does not fully capture per-flow requirements. Should future versions of 5G-LENA enable scheduling directly at the LC level, the scheduler implementation will be revised and extended accordingly.

VI. EVALUATION

This section discusses the performance analysis of the proposed scheduler. We assess the behavior exhibited by the two implementations that were previously discussed: the one based on linear programming, and the sorting-based algorithmic approach. The main objective of the evaluation is to assess the feasibility of the GFBR-aware scheduler, and compare its performance with that of schedulers already implemented in 5G-LENA, such as RR, MR, PF, and QoS-aware.

The performance of all the schedulers is evaluated in a simple topology containing a gNB and a number of UEs. The scenario configuration is detailed in Table III. All the UEs generate XR traffic. In particular, VR and CG flows, whose characteristics are depicted in Table IV. As shown, VR traffic is configured with a more demanding QoS profile, 5QI=87, corresponding to a Delay-critical GBR as the resource type, compared to the GBR resource type used for the CG traffic with 5QI=3. Consequently, VR traffic has a lower PDB and a priority level that corresponds to greater urgency. For the GFBR, different values are assigned to each traffic type, which vary across scenarios based on the particular traffic generated by the applications, the QoS profile, and the reference values provided in [32].

In the following, we analyze the scheduler performance across different setups. First, we consider an FR1 band scenario with a $\mu = 0$ numerology, so that the slot length of 1 ms and an RB width of 180 KHz. Subsequently, the carrier frequency is increased to FR2 band (mmWave) and $\mu = 3$ numerology is employed, leading to a time slot of 0.125 ms and RB width of 1440 KHz. In general, each RB has 12 subcarriers, where 3 of them are used for reference signals, so there are 9 subcarriers that can be effectively used for data transmission in each RB. In the time domain, there are 14 symbols. The first is for DL control and the 7th is for UL

TABLE III: Configuration of the evaluation setup.

Parameter	Value
Application duration	120 sec.
Number of UEs	4
Numerology (μ)	0 / 3
Carrier frequency	4 GHz / 30 GHz
Bandwidth	40 – 100 MHz / 100 – 400 MHz
gNB Tx power	41 dBm
UE Tx power	23 dBm
gNB antenna height	25 m / 3 m
UE antenna height	1.5 m / 1 m
gNB antenna array	1 TXRU: 4 × 8 (3GPP elements)
gNB antenna element gain	8 dBi
UE antenna array	1 TXRU: 1 × 1 (isotropic element)
UE antenna element gain	0 dBi
gNB noise figure	5 dB
UE noise figure	7 dB
Noise power spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz
Propagation model	3GPP UMa/Indoor TR 38.901
Channel condition	LoS
Duplexing mode	TDD
TDD pattern	DDDDDDU
PDCP Discarding Timer	5 ms for 5QI = 87, 50 ms for 5QI = 3

TABLE IV: Configuration of the XR traffic.

Virtual Reality traffic		Cloud Gaming traffic	
Number of flows	1	Number of flows	1
5QI value	87	5QI value	3
Av. rate offered	45/60 Mbps	Av. rate offered	30/45 Mbps
FPS	120	FPS	120

control. Therefore, only 12 symbols can be filled with data in each slot.

We divide the evaluation into three scenarios. The first one is devoted to assess the behavior of the proposed solution. The second one aims to compare its performance with existing alternatives. Then, the third scenario presents how the proposed scheme can be configured to bound the queues occupancy and then the delay.

A. Scenario with mobility, multi-user, and mixed XR traffic

First, we consider a simple scenario consisting of 1 gNB and 4 UEs who are using both VR and CG traffic with GFBRs of 30 and 15 Mbps, respectively. A bandwidth of 40 MHz is configured, enabling a maximum throughput of 130 Mbps under optimal conditions (maximum MCS of 28 for all users, corresponding to 64-QAM) [33]. All the UEs are located in the same beam and at a fixed distance from the gNB. The specific 2D location of UEs is illustrated in Figure 5. During the 30 initial seconds of the simulation, all UEs stay static at a distance of 120 meters from the gNB, and having the same distance between each other. During the interval between 30 and 40 seconds two UEs, one of each category, move away from the gNB, covering a distance of 60 meters during the 10 seconds. From seconds 40 to 70, these UEs stand still. This period of time in the experiment is characterized by a saturation situation since the available resources are insufficient to meet the requirements of all the UEs. Consequently, the scheduler role is of pivotal importance in ensuring optimal resource allocation. At second 70, the UEs

Fig. 5: Location of the UEs in relation to the gNB.

who had previously moved away, start getting closer to the gNB, reaching their original location 10 seconds later.

Figure 6 shows the temporal evolution of the throughput virtual queues over time, including the stability for all UE queues. As it can be observed, during the initial period in which the UEs remain stationary and close to the gNB, all queues are rather stable, evincing the fulfillment of the GFBR requirement. On the other hand, when UE 2 (VR2) and UE 4 (CG2) move away, at second 30, their queues show a clear reaction, resulting in an unstable situation, due to channel degradation caused by longer distances. This is more clearly seen for the 2nd UE (VR2).

The scheduler reaction to such channel degradation is illustrated in Figures 7 and 8, which depict the average RBs allocation and the average throughput for each UE calculated using 2 second intervals (the duration of the averaging window), respectively. Additionally, the GFBRs for both traffic types are indicated with dashed lines in the Figure 8. As can be observed, at second 30, the amount of RBs assigned to the 4th UE (CG2) is decreasing, due to channel degradation: the scheduler prioritizes those UEs with the best channel conditions, as the potential throughput is higher for these UEs. Nevertheless, the reduction in RBs stops when the 4th UE (CG2) approaches a point of being unable to meet the GFBR, which occurs approximately at second 40. Similarly, the 2nd UE (VR2) gets most of the allocated resources when required to meet the GFBR, which is greater for the VR traffic. As can be observed in Figure 8, the scheduler strives to ensure that the throughput of every UE reaches, at least, the corresponding GFBR. As scheduling decisions are made, the overall result is a trend towards queue stabilization, encompassing both physical (traffic) and virtual throughput queues.

The situation turns at second 70, when both UEs return to their original positions. This is clearly reflected in the throughput evolution, as illustrated in Figure 8. When all UEs are back at their initial locations in the scenario, the throughputs equalize, with the average throughput being 45 Mbps, as observed at the beginning of the experiment.

As commented before, the behavior of the scheduler can be modified by means of the defined weights. In the afore-

Fig. 6: Virtual throughput queue stability.

Fig. 7: Average RBs allocation over time.

mentioned scenario, Figures 9 and 10 show RBs allocation and throughput, respectively, obtained for different values of V , while parameters ω_1 and ω_2 are set to 1. For the sake of clarity, the total number of RBs allocated for all UEs is included in Figure 9, while Figure 10 only shows the performance of the two UEs that are on the move. As can be observed, the amount of allocated resources gets lower as V increases. These results evince that the scheduler is capable of achieving the proposed objectives with the minimal amount of resources. This is illustrated when $V = 250$, which ensures the throughput fulfills the GFBR for all users, i.e. 30 Mbps for the VR UEs and 15 Mbps for the CG UEs.

B. Performance Comparison

In this section we compare the behavior of the proposed scheduler with that of alternative solutions that have been previously deployed in 5G-LENA, analyzed in the existing literature: RR, MR, PF, and QoS-aware schedulers.

Figure 11 uses boxplots to show the amount of resources assigned to each type of UEs (i.e. VR and CG). Meanwhile, Figure 12 shows the throughput achieved by each UE cate-

Fig. 8: Average throughput over time.

Fig. 9: Total RBs allocation over time for different values of V .

Fig. 10: Average throughput over time for different values of V .

gory, also with boxplots. The lower and upper edges of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. Besides, the whiskers indicate 1.5 times the Inter Quartile Range (IQR), which represent approximately the 2 and 98 percentiles. A circle marks the average values. Both figures include the scheduling decisions made by each scheduler at each time slot during an experiment that lasts 10 seconds. This is done after 20 independent runs to guarantee that the channel state does not have a significant impact on the results, and so ensure statistical tightness. A numerology of 0 has been used, resulting in the collection of $1e4$ decisions per simulation, that is, $2e5$ decisions are considered for each boxplot. Furthermore, a range of bandwidths has been also added, starting from 40 MHz, which corresponds to a configuration where the capacity is not enough to meet traffic and QoS requirements, and goes up to 100 MHz. The corresponding requirements are 45 Mbps and 30 Mbps for VR and CG UEs, respectively.

As can be seen, the average allocated RBs and throughput are greater for the VR UEs for the proposed and the QoS-aware schedulers. This was expected, as these are the only scheduling alternatives that prioritize the UEs according their QoS characteristics. Nevertheless, the proposed solution is the one that best approaches meeting the GFBR for all UEs, even in the most challenging scenarios. In situations where the available bandwidth is higher, the different scheduling strategies yield similar behaviors, with the exception of the simplest alternative, RR, which performs slightly worse than the others. This is due to the fact that the channel state is not taken into account in its decision-making process.

Similarly, Figures 13 and 14 show the same performance indicators, but this time for the FR2 band, in particular with a frequency of 30 GHz and a numerology setting of $\mu = 3$. The

(a) VR UEs

(b) CG UEs

Fig. 11: Average RBs allocation over time for FR1 band.

bandwidths are also wider, thus allowing for a greater number of UEs, which are increased to 12 (6 with VR traffic and 6 with CG traffic), with their GFBRs set to 60 Mbps and 45 Mbps, respectively.

As was already seen, the proposed scheduler yields strong improvements in scenarios where resources are limited, and its resource allocation is optimal in order to fulfill throughput requirements defined in the corresponding 5G QoS profiles. Conversely, in scenarios with spare capacity to meet user demands, it provides the configurable feature of reducing the number of allocated resources. In the current evaluation, queue weights are set to 1, which corresponds to the default configuration. This default setting has proven to be effective across a range of scenarios, adapting well to varying traffic conditions. However, if we wanted to specifically address a particular objective or behavior, the weights could be adjusted accordingly, as outlined in Section IV.

C. Effect of Scheduler Configurations on Latency

As previously mentioned in Section IV-D, the proposed scheduler is able to tune its operation, based on a set of configuration parameters. In [29], the authors provide a method to find the V value that prevents queues from exceeding a specified threshold. In the context of our study, this possibility is particularly relevant in scenarios where the current resources are enough to meet the demands of all users, ensuring the assumptions made in [29] are met. Under these circumstances, the proposed scheduler can be thus configured to minimize resource usage, while ensuring that queues remain below a pre-defined limit, thereby guaranteeing that the RLC sojourn time is bounded.

To provide an illustrative example of this capability, we focus on the VR service, which has the highest data rate of all the considered XR traffics in DL. It is mainly composed of a video stream, which entails a number of video frames,

Fig. 12: Average throughput in every averaging window over time for FR1 band.

Fig. 13: Average RBs allocation over time for FR2 band.

with a certain frame rate. An application packet is generated for each frame and is sent over one or more IP datagrams. Its length follows a truncated Gaussian distribution and the average inter-arrival time is inversely proportional to the frame rate. For instance, a frame rate of 120 fps corresponds to an inter-arrival time of 8.3 ms. However, the actual inter-arrival time is not fixed but rather subject to random fluctuations, which are accounted for by the jitter factor, also distributed according to a truncated Gaussian model [34].

In Figure 15 we set the packet size of the VR traffic generator to its maximum value, in order to evaluate the worst-case situation where the RLC buffer occupancy would reach

Fig. 14: Average throughput in every averaging window over time for FR2 band.

its largest value. Besides, in [29] the largest possible buffer occupancy is also used to configure the V value. The queue weights (i.e., ω_1 and ω_2) are set to 1. Figure 15 shows both the RLC buffer occupancy and sojourn delay at the left and right axis, respectively. The theoretical value of the buffer occupancy is depicted with dashed lines for three specific V values selected as illustrative examples. Then, the simulated buffer occupancy is depicted using solid lines, where the top and bottom lines indicate the maximum and average RLC buffer occupancy, respectively. As can be observed, the remarkable difference between queue maximum and mean values obtained during the simulations evinces the high variability in VR traffic pattern due to traffic bursts. Finally, the figure includes boxplots that represents the distribution of the sojourn time for different V values. The theoretical maximum delay is numerically represented for regions between dashed lines.

The figure clearly shows three illustrative situations, $V \leq 103$, $V \leq 267$ and $V \leq 535$, from more to less restrictive in terms of maximum queue size, but with the consequence of a reduction in the use of resources. It is worth noting that we can effectively define a maximum waiting time, thanks to being able to bound the maximum queue length. For instance, to avoid exceeding a waiting time of 10.8 ms, and given that the average application rate is, in this worst case scenario, 62.35 Mbps (the highest rate for a 3GPP video stream configured with 45 Mbps as the average data rate), the queue size should not exceed 6.75 Mbits. By applying the formula shown in Section IV-D and [29], we find that the maximum value for V is 103. Therefore, if the scheduler is configured with a value of $V \leq 103$, and each UE has a VR traffic of 45 Mbps or less, we can guarantee that the delay induced by the RLC enqueue will always be less than 10.8 ms. This result is valid provided that the system has enough capacity to ensure a queue length reduction in an event of a queue surpassing the

Fig. 15: Waiting times in the RLC queue and the maximum and average size of the queue for one of the UEs as a function of V .

maximum admissible size, minus the VR packet length. As can be observed in Figure 15, the simulated maximum queue occupancy matches the theoretical values, evincing that the bound is valid.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a new multi-objective QoS-aware Lyapunov-based MAC scheduler. It is designed to ensure the network stability, guarantee that the time-average throughput fulfills the GBR requirement established by the corresponding flow 5QI, and maximize the overall throughput, by prioritizing those UEs with the best channel conditions. Moreover, we have added a number of configuration knobs by means of certain weights, which allow us to tune the operation of the scheduler, for instance fostering a more effective radio resource usage, thereby enhancing the scheduler adaptability to a broader range of scenarios, or bounding the traffic delay.

The proposed scheme has been implemented in the 5G-LENA framework and compared with the other existing solutions. The performance evaluation shows that proposed solution fulfills throughput requirements under any load condition, provided the system capacity is not exceeded. In this latter case the scheduler tends to prioritize users with better channel conditions. In addition, the requirement fulfillment does not require higher resource utilization.

In our future work, we aim to expand the model presented herewith in various ways. First, we will analyze the performance of the underlying optimization problem when adding more complex functions, for instance logarithmic, to foster different trade-offs between resource consumption and queue stabilization. Additionally, we will extend its design to tackle delay explicitly in the schedulers, particularly designed to foster Delay-critical GBR flows. We will thus extend the number of metrics considered by the scheduler to enhance its versatility to satisfy the increasing requirements of novel services, such as XR. In this sense, we will also focus on studying different scheduling policies, to identify the optimum configuration for a broad range of setups. We will exploit Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques to support the configuration of the scheduler when required, thereby adapting its operation to changes in UE features, traffic patterns, QoS requirements, or channel conditions. For this purpose, we plan to develop an xApp within the RAN Intelligent Controller

(RIC) framework, enabling the dynamic reconfiguration of the scheduler in real time.

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